

STUDENTS BIBBLE

A student bible written from not scientific students

A simple guide for your Master Thesis

CLEAR QUESTION

– Finding a clear question is a big step

It is nice to follow your passions and interests in the topic that created the character of your research. *Make sure your question is up to date and have the potential to become a new word.*

– The first question/ task could be very wide. Talk to people who have expertise or the practical experience in it, be interested in the details. After the talks you most probably will see the particular angle of the wide question.

It is good to have one question. A clear question could consist of subquestions. You can decide between question or hypothesis. Proving the hypothesis we ask if it is true or false.

An essential design research question points into the problem solving, dilemma clarifying, being a precise element of the big system.

A clear question (or task) creates the framework what is important and less for the state of art.

The research question could be corrected by the end of the research.

The question should not be predefined for the research.

VALUE

Modesty: I see my research as a piece of the pizza.

APPROPRIATE METHODS

Here are some suggestions of useful methods that can serve you during your research phase. These can and probably should be mixed and adapted to your own topic. Think about to make the method fit to your question. Choose the appropriate methods for answering it.

Desk research (quantitative)

During this research try to gather as much as possible knowledge from books, papers, reports and articles that others have already written. So you investigate already existing knowledge and absorb it. Also study the related practices which are already exist carefully to understand the field even more.

- Literature research (secondary research)
- State of the Art research (Case studies, best practise examples)

Primary research (Field research, qualitative)

This means moving to the field of action to understand what is actually working or not. Talk to stakeholders or relevant actors to form your own perspective and get the information first hand.

- Face-to-face interviews with stakeholders
- Surveys
- Observation

Case study research

Another possible method is to explain and answer your point through a case study. Here you investigate your question or hypothesis through an example which makes it practical and gives it a real picture.

- Prove hypothesis/answer question through an example

Exploratory research

By experimenting and exploring through making you can test and research parallelly. This gives you the opportunity to directly get some feedback on ideas and develop new starting points.

- Workshops
- Testing
- Ideation

Applied research

Making use of applied research you can investigate your solution proposals on your stakeholders and gain knowledge.

VALUE

Self-efficacy: I use specific techniques.

THINKING ABOUT WHAT OTHERS HAVE THOUGHT

– If you don't know how to start your state-of-the-art research: the most important and up to date information of the design (or academic) community you want to participate you can find using social media nowadays.

– Even this quick desktop research helps you to find related literature, videos, podcasts and other examples which would be useful for your topic.

A lot of things of which you are thinking have already been done and you see them the more you research because you are not the only intelligent person.

– It also helpful for real case studies examples because you even can contact a person who wrote a related book to your topic or designed a project directly via email or messenger this that is possible nowadays.

– But you shouldn't forget about literature research after you find the books you want to read because it makes a completely different experience of giving you more either subquestions or answers to you research questions/hypothesis while reading and exploring the book.

– State-of-the-art can't only be found in the literature or digital resources. It also exists in the real world: for example at the design exhibitions or museums, conferences, observation in the town - everything what is happening around you.

VALUE

Acknowledgement: I'm standing on the shoulders of giants and I'm on the way with peers.

THOUGHTS AND EXPERIENCES OF OTHERS ON METHODS

Learning from other people's thoughts and experience is not a shame. From the failures and successes of others, we see more than one result. It's more about the way predecessors tried and the feedback they got. We can rethink problems and improve or re-summarize our solutions based on the practice of others. Choose some methods that you think are smart, try and improve, and contribute your own talents on the basis of predecessors.

VALUE

Frugality: Help each other to reach research goals by benefiting from each others methods knowledge.

GIVE MY RESULTS TO ALL INTERESTED PEOPLE

– Once you find your results, take a five-minute break and take a breath.

– Define the most important points of the results and the priorities of the results.

– Don't write about your results at the moment. You can use diagrams or maps to help you.

– Use and help yourself by using a colour code to structure your results and make them visible.

– Save time and resources, and remember to ask for help or feedback from other students.

– Create a story with the results and make them tangible to make them interesting.

– Write down and analyse what you have learnt from the results.

– Write a short recapitulation concerning the origin of the results and only the most important points.

– Scalability of results and development for the next steps.

– The results could open new questions.

– Show your resources to people and share what you have learnt.

VALUE

Togetherness: building a community.

EDITORS

Supervisor: Dr. Christof Arn

Students:

Anastasiia Bekasova

Gaia Leonardi

Tonghua Shen

Anastasija Jovicic

Magdalena Tomoff

Sofiiia Kaminska

Kseniia Marchenko

Daria Leush